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**THE ROLE OF LECTURERS IN USING VIRTUAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AS A SUPPORT
TO CONVENTIONAL EDUCATION IN EKITI STATE UNIVERSITY, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the role of lecturers in using a virtual learning environment to support conventional education at Ekiti State University. The purpose of the study was to determine the impacts of virtual classrooms on teaching and learning at Ekiti State University. The study adopted a descriptive research design of survey type. The population consists of 7,719 students in all the faculties out of which two faculties were selected through a multistage procedure, a sample size of 200 was used for the study. A structured questionnaire was designed to collect the information required for the study. Data gathered were analysed with the use of mean and standard deviation. The study revealed that the students of Ekiti State University are aware of the possible merits of adopting a virtual learning environment into their educational environment. Therefore, it was recommended that university management provide well-equipped laboratories that will enhance the effective dissemination of knowledge in the virtual learning environment and that both lecturers and students be trained on how to use virtual learning to deliver and receive lectures.

Keywords: Virtual Learning, Conventional Environment, University Education, Teaching and Learning

INTRODUCTION

The advent of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) gave rise to the institution of virtual classrooms or virtual world. Information and communication technology has rapidly covered all nations of the world, improving the technological awareness of students and various individuals in their pursuit to acquire diverse knowledge to harness their professional dreams (Al Rawashdeh et al., 2021). The application of information technology tools in classroom learning and methodology for teaching helps to improve the quality of education in schools, universities, and institutions (Castro & Tumibay, 2021, pp. 1368). With this explosive awareness of technological knowledge, the higher education environment is expected to expand focus on meeting students' expectations with more attention to widening the students' greater involvement in ICT. It is through this ICT that students could develop lifelong learning skills that would enable them to cope with emergencies of new subject disciplines and greater use of technology in learning. The potential of ICT to inspire students to achieve greater success cannot be overemphasised. Through ICT, innovative learning approaches such as virtual learning are already being widely explored both in traditional and non-traditional educational settings throughout the nation. Moreover, students' demand for on-line learning has also increased from all walks of life (Castro & Tumibay, 2021). On this basis, Al

Rawashdeh et al. (2021) noted that the utilisation of relevant virtual learning has never been more important and should therefore be a significant element of this generation's approach to education, socialising, and normalising.

Before the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic, virtual learning was growing approximately at the rate of 15.4% yearly in educational institutions around the world (Alqahtani & Rajkhan, 2020). However, during COVID-19, the situation changed dramatically to approximately 60% and beyond (WHO, 2020). Many educational institutions began to provide most of their services via several online platforms, including virtual learning (Al Rawashdeh et al., 2021). Lecturers and students were forced to adopt the virtual learning environment to achieve their educational purposes. Since the post-COVID-19 era, many institutions in Nigeria have adopted blended learning, which is a mix of traditional and virtual learning environments. Perhaps due to some derived economic advantages of virtual learning such as cost effectiveness, time management, and other benefits.

Learning is dynamic, and it is part of human existence. Each day of a man's life, he learns new things to survive in a changing world. As a man interacts with his environment at any stage in time, he learns new things. According to Singh (2011), learning starts at home in a cradle format and continues in school, college, universities, and workplace in a formal learning setting. As the 21st century unfolds, learning is breaking out of the narrow boxes that it was trapped in during the 20th century, lecturers' professionalism, reflection, and ingenuity are leading learning to places genuinely exciting to this new generation of young school students who connect with their lecturers. Anekwe (2017) thus argued that virtual learning environments (VLE) expose students beyond the confines of a particular building, and they are neither limited to a single location or instant.

The school learning environment offers opportunities for lecturers and students to come together for the institutional teaching/learning process. In this learning process, various technological gadgets are now available and are employed to facilitate the process. Such advanced technologies include the Internet, e-mail, website, mobile phone, iPod, etc. (Mangal & Mangal, 2019). These advanced technologies are variable tools that provide valuable assistance and are a good alternative to traditional methods of education. This alternative could be in the form of a virtual classroom.

The conventional method also known as the traditional method of teaching and learning is a gathering that allows lecturers and students to converge in the classroom to teach and learn (Longjohn & Audu, 2020). A virtual learning environment involves the interaction of lecturers and students on the Internet without physical recognition (Palden, 2020). According to Berrett (2012), in a traditional classroom, where the teacher controls the flow of knowledge and information, students are expected to continue learning a subject after school through homework assignments. This model is where the time, place and pace of learning of students remain constant. The conventional model of learning ceases to be relevant when there is a disruption in the school system and teachers are restrained from reaching their students directly via face-to-face classroom environment. This situation may require a switch to an alternative virtual learning environment, as was experienced globally during the recent Covid-19 pandemic.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Since the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic and the post-covid era, the use of virtual learning has become a significant part of institutional teaching and learning systems. Lecturers and students have benefited from the incorporation of virtual learning into the educational system. Research has shown that it resulted in the reduction of student costs while improving the quality of learning and teaching. It also indicated that it is economical for students as they can perform other useful activities outside of learning periods in their spare time. Additionally, flexibility in learning is gained, as it provides

learners with the benefits of taking classes anywhere and anytime. However, some of the advantages observed, including accessibility to technology and limited power supply, have been reported in some institutions and less privileged countries like Nigeria.

Based on the observed advantages of the use of virtual classroom learning, educational institutions have opened their doors to virtual learning to complement face-to-face traditional learning for course delivery to date. At Ekiti State University, lecturers are allowed to deliver their lectures virtually and conduct continuous assessment tests online through the University e-learning portal when necessary to avoid a break in the academic calendar, particularly during temporary disruptions and the early period of the semester. Therefore, it becomes essential to understand the impact of the application of virtual learning to facilitate teaching and learning and complement conventional face-to-face learning at Ekiti State University.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study was to determine the impact of a virtual learning environment as a support to conventional education at Ekiti State University. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the perceived impacts of virtual classrooms on Ekiti State University students' learning
2. Investigate the extent to which Ekiti State University students are prepared to participate in virtual classrooms.
3. Determine the areas of improvement as perceived by students from Ekiti State University for improving teaching in virtual classrooms.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What perceived impacts do virtual classrooms have on Ekiti State University students' learning?
2. To what extent do Ekiti State University students participate in virtual classrooms?
3. What are the areas of improvement perceived by students from Ekiti State University for improving traditional teaching through virtual classrooms?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of a Virtual Learning Environment

The virtual classroom has no single definition because the system is characterised by learning without time or space. Learning is continuously adopting new formats involving advanced technologies such as multimedia, the internet, blogs, websites, mobile phones, and wikis as these are accessed on the internet (Kovtoniuk et al., 2022). Virtual learning is not confined to the walls of a traditional classroom. According to Lokie (2011), Virtual learning makes it possible to access, analyse, generate, exchange, and apply data, information, and knowledge in ways that were nearly unthinkable until recently by utilising internet facilities, platforms, satellite links, and associated technologies. In effect, it involves the learning acquired by students through the interaction of digitally delivered content. It involves network-based inputs and tutoring support obtained on no-line tools and media such as the Internet, intranets, extranets, simulations and games, virtual worlds, clouds, satellite broadcasts, and web platforms (Al-Handhali et al., 2020). Arkorful and Abaidoo (2015) argued that learning can be realised through the use and integration of electronic discourses, such as e-mail, portal, downloadable - executable file Facebook, social networks, electronic dissertations on web platforms and eportfolios, among others. Moreso, Kharbach (2013), opined that mobile learning is the ability to obtain or provide educational content on personal pocket devices such as PDAs, smartphones, and mobile phones. These devices help students realise their virtual learning potential.

The virtual classroom is realised through various processes such as online learning, web-based training, and technology-delivered instructions. All these virtual learning environments (VLEs) are defined as computer-based

environments that are relatively open systems. They operate by allowing interactions and encounters with other participants who have equal access to a wide range of resources (Pelet & Lecarte, 2013). Pererva et al. (2020), Kovtoniuk et al. (2022), and Wagner et al. (2008), all agree that VLEs provide tools that are customised for education. Even in higher education, these tools have become very popular for learning among students due to the increase in internet technology.

The virtual classroom is based on Information and Communication Technology. Tertiary institutions should integrate virtual learning effectively into their systems because the world is becoming more technologically inclined. Oye et al. (2012) referred to the new technological trend in an e-driven world. This e-driven world has brought unimaginable changes in all aspects of life. Consequently, students should be well equipped through virtual learning to provide them with the necessary experiences for personal growth and development.

A virtual classroom is an online setting that enables people to participate in live training sessions without having to travel (Turoff, 2007). You can sit in the comfort of your environment and listen to lectures. You can participate in lab exercises, ask questions, and effectively interact with the teacher as if the action is taking place in a conventional classroom, but it is done with the convenience of technological gadgets such as desktops that have Internet and phone connection. The Internet, on the other hand, provides such advantages and new ways of communicating, interacting, and assessing information for both lecturers and students (Anekwe, 2017).

Concept of Conventional/Traditional Education

Traditional education, also known as back-to-basics, conventional education, face-to-face, or customary education, refers to long-established customs that society traditionally used in schools (Gowda & Suma, 2017; Osadcha et al., 2021). Some forms of education reform promote the adoption of progressive education practices, a more holistic approach that focusses on individual students' needs and self-control. In the eyes of reformers, traditional teacher-centred methods focused on rote learning and memorisation must be abandoned in favour of student-centred and task-based approaches to learning (Lipeikien, 2003).

Traditional learning starts from the idea of total control of the teacher over students in the way a curricular content is taught (Novak, 2003). In other words, the teacher conceives their students as "empty holes" in knowledge, and only through their teachings the "holes" can be "filled" (Novak, 2003: 128). El Sadik and Al Abdulmonem (2021) emphasise the passive role of students in a traditional classroom in which a rigid explanation of phenomena given by the teacher is imposed. In addition, repetition and memorisation of concepts and written tests focused only on theory as instruments of evaluation of a course (Novak, 2003). In traditional teaching, students' interests are not taken into account, and information is transmitted in the same way to everybody (Bouwmeester et al., 2016; Shin and Brock, 2017).

Theoretical Support for Virtual Classroom

Constructivism is a concept that indicates that knowledge is constructed through an individual's association with a given environment (Erbil, 2020). In Vygotsky theory, individuals construct knowledge of their own when they are actively involved in learning by doing and sharing ideas with peers (Vygotsky, 1987). In the process, the learner uses sensory knowledge to construct meaning from a given task. This concept believes in interacting with the environment by navigating through physical space, reading skills, field trips, research projects, workshops, and presentations (Anekwe, 2017). Constructivists place a great emphasis on collaborative learning principles; they encourage active learning. Virtual learning is one of the core technologies that supports constructive learning (Jonassen et al., 2000). In virtual classrooms, the process

of transferring information in traditional classrooms goes outside the classrooms through ICT and Internet devices. Information transfer and interactive activities occur within an active learning environment (Berrett, 2012).

METHODOLOGY

The research adopted the design of the case study survey. The study is considered a case study because it is considered the case of Ekiti State University in the southwestern region of Nigeria. It is a survey design because it involves collecting data from a sampled population to describe the characteristics as they exist in the study population. The population consisted of 7,719 students from all faculties at Ekiti State University. The multistage sampling technique was used to select samples for the study. Two faculties were selected from the nine faculties of the institution for the study. Then four departments were selected from each of the two faculties. 25 respondents were randomly selected from each of the eight departments. The sample size consisted of 200 (200) respondents randomly selected from the two faculties. A closed-ended structured questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection. Two types of Likert scale were used in the instrument. The items for research questions 1 and 3 used the scale, Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1); while items in research question 2 used the scale of Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2), Very Low Extent (1). The instrument was face and content validated by experts from the Faculty of Education of Ekiti State University. The reliability of the instrument was ensured using the Cronbach Alpha reliability method. The reliability index of the instrument was found to be 0.77 which was considered adequate for the instrument. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean scores, and standard deviations. The decision rule for the two four-point scales is a mean of 2.50 as mid-point. The means score of respondents equal to or greater 2.50 is rated as agree or high extent. On the other hand, the mean scores below this level are regarded as disagree or low extent.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What perceived impacts do virtual classrooms have on the learning of students at Ekiti State University?

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of the perceived impacts of Virtual Classrooms on Ekiti State University Students’ Learning

S/N	Items	n	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	I learnt collaboratively with others from a diverse environment	200	2.60	0.49	Agree
2	I have developed problem-solving skills in virtual classes.	200	2.64	0.48	Agree
3	I enjoyed the lessons and has encouraged me to do my homework by myself.	200	2.43	0.50	Disagree
4	I learnt at my own pace within and outside of the school.	200	2.54	0.50	Agree
5	The virtual classroom helps me to follow my lessons repeatedly	200	2.33	0.47	Disagree

Table 1 reveals that respondents agree that virtual classes support collaborative learning (2.60) and problem-solving skills (2.64). They also feel that virtual learning allows self-paced study as indicated in the mean score (2.54). However, the students disagree that virtual classes motivate them to complete homework independently (2.43). They also do not strongly feel that virtual classes help them review lessons repeatedly (2.33). Generally, the standard deviations are low (between 0.47

and 0.50), indicating consistent responses across participants. From the above table, it could be said that virtual classes are beneficial for collaboration, problem-solving, and self-paced learning, at Ekiti State University. However, improvements are needed in student motivation for independent study and lesson review

Research Question 2: To what extent do students at Ekiti State University participate in virtual classrooms?

Table 2: Descriptive analysis of the extent of participation of Ekiti state university students to participate in virtual classrooms

S/N	Item	n	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Confidence in Online Studies	200	2.74	0.44	High extent
2	Accessibility to ICT facilities	200	2.54	0.50	High extent
3	Courses in virtual classroom support self-reliance	200	2.65	0.40	High extent
4	Preparedness to study in virtual classroom	200	2.51	0.50	High extent
5	Encouraged to register for virtual courses	200	2.76	0.43	High extent

Table 2 shows a high extent mean score of 2.74 from the respondents indicating that they are confident that they will do well in their online studies. On having enough accessibility to ICT facilities, the mean score was 2.54, indicating that the response was of high extent, the respondents have enough access to ICT facilities. Item number 3 recorded a mean score of 2.65 indicates that virtual classroom will make them self-reliant in their studies. The 2.51 mean score in item 4 shows that the respondents were prepared to continue to study in the virtual classroom, a high degree was recorded. The last item also recorded a high mean score of 2.76 as the respondents reported that they are always encouraged to register courses in virtual classrooms. From the above, it could be said that the degree to which students at Ekiti State University are prepared to participate in virtual classrooms is high.

Research Question 3: What are the areas of improvement perceived by students from Ekiti State University for improving traditional teaching through the virtual classrooms?

Table 3: Descriptive Analysis of the areas of improvement perceived by students from Ekiti State University to improve their teaching in virtual classrooms

S/N	Items	n	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	More computers/laptops should be provided for students use.	200	2.77	0.42	Agree
2	Lecturers should be trained and re-trained to achieve greater competency in virtual classroom operations.	200	2.36	0.48	Disagree
3	Provision of steady power supply	200	2.86	0.34	Agree
4	Free access to the Internet networks	200	2.75	0.43	Agree
5	Internet connectivity to be done in all classes and computer laboratories	200	2.82	0.38	Agree

Table 3 shows that the mean values range from 2.36 to 2.86, which indicates that most respondents agree with the statements but with varying levels of consensus. Provision of steady power supply has the highest mean (M = 2.86) with a low SD (0.34), meaning that a large majority strongly support this recommendation with little variation in responses. Internet

connectivity in all classes and labs ($M = 2.82$, $SD = 0.38$) also has strong agreement with minimal variation. Lecturers' training and re-training ($M = 2.36$, $SD = 0.48$) has the lowest mean score, meaning fewer respondents agreed on this compared to other items. A relatively higher standard deviation (0.48) suggests greater variation in responses, implying a mix of opinions on whether lecturers need more training. It could be said from the above that highest priority for improvement is steady power supply and internet connectivity, as they had the highest agreement levels. Overall, respondents generally agree on the need for more ICT infrastructure to enhance virtual learning as perceived by the Ekiti State University students for enhancement of teaching and learning in virtual classroom.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The study's finding in the first research question revealed that virtual classrooms have a positive impact on the learning of Ekiti State University students, its positive impact is the result of the students' ability to learn collaboratively with others from diverse environments. This is followed by learning at your own pace within and outside the school. From the first research question, it could be said that problem solving skills, collaborative learning, and self-paced learning are the positive impact of virtual classrooms on the learning of Ekiti State University students. This corroborates the findings of Cacault et al. (2021) that having access to live-streamed lectures in addition to an in-person option improves the achievement of students. Turnbull et al. (2021) equally argued the significance of virtual learning training as support for faculty members and students, and suggested a technology-enhanced learning hub for delivering higher education which will maximally impact on students learning.

The study in question two revealed that virtual learning enables and grants students' confidence that they will do well in their online studies. It is also revealed that when students have enough access to ICT facilities, they are encouraged to participate to a large extent in virtual classrooms. The study of Al-Handhali et al. (2020) confirmed that virtual learning enhances communication and interaction between students and teachers, with 80% of students affirming the benefits of virtual classrooms. Furthermore, the findings revealed that the degree to which Ekiti State University students are prepared to participate in virtual classrooms is high.

More so, the findings of the study in research question three show that there is a need for a steady power supply for lecturers' enhancement of their teaching in virtual classrooms. The provision of more computers/laptops for students' use was ranked highest among all the available facilities influencing virtual learning in Ekiti State University followed by the internet connectivity to be done in all classes and computer laboratories; this could be because third-generation wireless networks provide unfettered broadband internet access and wireline broadband DSL access through local exchanges. This study was supported by Al Rawashdeh et al. (2021), Alqahtani, and Rajkhan (2020) that virtual learning has a strategy for executing educational and corporate training and suggested that readiness for virtual learning implementation will significantly impact educational outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Despite the considerable roles that lecturers play in using virtual learning environments to support conventional education at Ekiti State University, there are voids in virtual teaching and learning systems. Specifically, some sensitive electronic equipment like computers is prone to problems when exposed to unreliable power supplies, and this may cause components to operate outside of normal values in virtual classrooms. Through the findings made, it was concluded that the provision of internet connectivity and free access to internet networks are areas of improvement, as perceived by students of Ekiti State University, for the enhancement of their teaching in virtual classrooms.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study considered the complementary roles of virtual learning in the traditional face-to-face method. It was discovered, however, that some factors impact on the complementary roles from being fully beneficial to the students. These findings underpinned the reasons for the following recommendations.

1. Government to intervene by providing enabling infrastructures such as well-equipped laboratories, active Internet networks and other ICT facilities such functional laptops for lecturers that will enhance the effective dissemination of knowledge in the virtual learning environment.
2. Both lecturers and students should further be trained on how to use virtual learning to prepare, deliver, and receive lectures by lecturers.
3. Assignments and lectures could be strictly observed on-line, and solutions should also be submitted online.
4. Strategies such as interactive lesson formats, gamification, and enhanced lesson accessibility may help improve engagement and motivation in virtual learning environments.

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